

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICE ON ANTIBIOTIC USE AND ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE AMONG TENANTS OF BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 7

Pages: 701-725

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1996

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12638908

Manuscript Accepted: 05-31-2024

Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice on Antibiotic Use and Antimicrobial Resistance among Tenants of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

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Abstract

Antimicrobial resistance occurs when germs develop the ability to resist the drugs designed to kill them. It is regarded as a threat to global health; however, few people are aware of it. This study aims to determine the knowledge, attitude, and practice of tenants of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. Using purposive quota sampling, two hundred respondents aged 18 and above were selected to answer a two-part survey questionnaire. The results showed that 92 respondents have a good knowledge of antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance, while 81 have moderate knowledge, and 27 have poor knowledge. The overall attitudes of the respondents were found to be positive, but their practices were considered poor. A significant difference in the level of knowledge was found according to age and educational attainment; however, no significant difference was found in terms of socioeconomic status. In terms of attitude, a significant difference in age, educational attainment, and socioeconomic status has been found. Also, the level of knowledge was reported not to be significantly related in terms of practices. However, a moderately low positive correlation was significant between the respondents' attitudes and practices. In a nutshell, the data and the results suggest that it is essential to improve the knowledge and attitudes of individuals on the use of antibiotics and the resistance thereof through an online campaign, and raising the issue to the government agencies in order to reduce the possibility of misuse and to lessen antimicrobial resistance.

Keywords: *antibiotic use, antimicrobial resistance, knowledge, attitude, practice*

Introduction

Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) is a serious, prevalent issue worldwide. It threatens the health of the public, as well as affects the progress of the economy. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), antibiotic resistance can lead to an increase in healthcare costs, prolonged hospital stays, and an increase in death rates. Furthermore, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2022) noted that antimicrobial resistance can potentially cause adverse effects on people at any stage of life, especially those in the healthcare, veterinary, and agriculture industries. Hence, it is recognized as one of the most urgent public health issues. In recent years, researchers have extensively studied individuals' stand towards the use of antibiotics and AMR. As reported by Lancet (2022), an estimated 4.95 million deaths were related to AMR in 2019, which includes approximately 1.27 million deaths directly caused by AMR due to the growth of drug resistance in diseases like lower respiratory infections, bacterial infections, HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria, etcetera. If antibiotics lose their effectiveness, it threatens the community as the public loses the ability to treat infections and control these public health threats, leading to deleterious effects (CDC, 2022).

Antibiotics are a type of antimicrobial medicine that is effective in fighting bacterial infection in humans and animals. They work by either killing the bacteria or inhibiting or slowing down the growth of bacteria and preventing them from multiplying (Felman, 2022). However, their use does not apply to everything; they are ineffective against viruses, and unnecessary intake can even be dangerous (John Hopkins Medicine [JHH], n.d). The misuse and overuse of antibiotics are known to be an essential factor in the increase of AMR pathogens (WHO, 2021). Numerous studies presented that most individuals had an acceptable or moderate level of knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) toward antibiotic use and AMR. This is closely followed by poor awareness of the subject. In 2018, Okedo-Alex et al. conducted a study in Nigeria that showed that 64.87% of the respondents had good knowledge of antibiotic use and AMR, and only 56% had good practice of antibiotic use. Contrastingly, in the study conducted by Lubwama et al. (2021), final-year medical students in East Africa have low scores in knowledge regarding antibiotic use and resistance in clinical scenarios. Furthermore, it was reported that 61% of the respondents admitted that they purchased antibiotics without a doctor's prescription.

Similarly, Horvat et al. (2022) reported that 42.8% of medical students in Serbia testified that they self-medicate. The results of the different studies suggest that the public's general knowledge, attitude, and practices toward the use of antibiotics and AMR range from poor to moderate. It implies that only a small number of the population have a high level of knowledge, attitude, and practice on antibiotic use and AMR.

Antimicrobial resistance is an urgent concern in public health, continuously becoming a more significant concern globally. The increase in the threat brought by AMR was made worse by disinformation, misinformation, and poor infection prevention and control (WHO, 2020). The study conducted by Vidad et al. (2022) in Manila stated that more than half of the respondents had a moderate level of knowledge, including 63 respondents. However, it was closely followed by 57 respondents who displayed poor knowledge. Additionally, they stated the findings of the Department of Health's Reference Laboratory for the Antimicrobial Resistance

Surveillance Program. It was found that “there has been an increasing number of bacterial organisms that have records showing Antibiotic resistance such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, and Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in the Philippines” (p.143). It was also discovered that having adequate knowledge and awareness of antibiotics and resistance is closely related to the attitude and practice on the use of antibiotics.

Thus, an intervention must be done at all levels of society (WHO, 2020). This not only lessens the chances of medicines becoming ineffective (Vidad et al., 2022) but also decreases the spread of resistance and reduces the deleterious impacts it imposes on the individual and the community (WHO, 2022).

Antibiotics

Antibiotics are powerful drugs that help the body ward off diseases and infections caused by bacteria. Antibiotics are otherwise known as antibacterial or antimicrobials (Patient UK, 2020). They work by “blocking vital processes in bacteria” (NPS MedicineWise, 2022), which kills the bacteria or prevents them from multiplying and spreading (NHS Inform, 2023). When used correctly, they quickly and effectively eliminate infections, causing people to feel better in a matter of days because they are fast-acting medicines and begin to work within a few hours. Anytime that antibiotics are used, like all drugs, they can cause side effects and even contribute to AMR. However, the intake of antibiotics only when necessary “makes the benefits usually outweigh the risk of side effects or antibiotic resistance” (CDC, 2021; Cleveland Clinic [CC], n.d.). Antibiotics are generally safe but can be equally harmful when misused and overused.

There are various classes of antibiotics, which include the following: Penicillin, Macrolides, Cephalosporins, Fluoroquinolones, Beta-lactams with increased activity, Urinary anti-infectives, and Lincosamides. The common antibiotics that physicians usually prescribe are amoxicillin (Amoxil), azithromycin and erythromycin, cephalexin and cefdinir, ciprofloxacin (Cipro) and levofloxacin (Levaquin), amoxicillin/clavulanate (Augmentin), nitrofurantoin (Macrobid), and clindamycin (Cleocin) (Felman, 2022).

Antibiotics are only effective in treating specific health conditions. Antibiotics fight infections caused by bacteria, which include strep throat, whooping cough, urinary infections, sepsis, bloodstream infections, skin abscess/impetigo, bacterial pneumonia, urinary tract infections, streptococcal pharyngitis, and some middle ear infections (JHH, 2019). Moreover, according to Felman (2022), antibiotics are also helpful in enhancing infection prevention and control during surgeries. However, even if used properly, they can still have common side effects like any other medication. It includes digestive problems such as nausea, diarrhea, vomiting, indigestion, bloating, loss of appetite, and stomach pain. According to Children’s Medical Center Dallas (CMCD, 2020), antibiotics can cause diarrhea or an upset stomach because antibiotics disrupt the ecosystem in the gut.

On the other hand, they do not work on viruses like flu, cold and runny nose, sore throats, and most cases of chest colds such as bronchitis. It must also be noted that some bacterial infections get better independently without antibiotics, like most sinus and ear infections (CDC, 2021). When antibiotics are misused and overused, they allow bacteria to adapt, and they become ineffective in treating infections since the bacteria grow resistant to the drug. That causes a longer course of treatment for an antibiotic, which in turn can bring more damage to the body’s immune system (Keck Medicine of USC, 2018). These more severe side effects include: “*C. diff* infection, which causes diarrhea that can lead to severe colon damage and death; severe and life-threatening allergic reactions; and antibiotic-resistant infections” (CDC, 2021, para. 4).

Antimicrobial Resistance

Antimicrobial agents are a large variety of chemical compounds and physical agents used to destroy microorganisms or prevent their development (Britanica, n.d). Depending on the traits of their target, these compounds may have a microbicide or bacteriostatic impact. Antimicrobial agents can be categorized based on their use to prevent infections and diseases caused by pathogens. Antibacterial drugs are used to inhibit the pathogenic activity of bacteria. Antifungal drugs are used to prevent fungal activity in the host. On the other hand, antiparasitic drugs are used to prevent the growth of pathogenic parasites (BYJUS, 2018).

Microorganisms can be seen only through a microscope, though it can offset these medicines’ potent effects under certain conditions. The ability of bacteria to withstand the effects of antimicrobial agents that intend to kill them causes this. The microorganisms then developed what is known as antimicrobial resistance. Antimicrobial resistance happens when microorganisms (such as bacteria, fungi, viruses, and parasites) change when exposed to antimicrobial drugs (such as antibiotics, antifungals, antivirals, antimalarials, and anthelmintics). Microorganisms that develop AMR are sometimes referred to as “superbugs.” As a result, the medicines become ineffective, and infections persist in the body, increasing the risk of spreading to others (Pan American Health Organization [PAHO], n.d).

There are several major contributing causes of AMR. Misuse and overuse of antimicrobials significantly contribute to the development of drug-resistant pathogens, leading to bacteria propagating at any opportunity. Bacteria reproduce even if a patient forgets to take medication for a day, stops treatment too soon, or uses incorrect antibiotics. Bacteria can undergo mutations as they multiply, eventually producing changes in structural or colony characteristics or the loss of responsiveness to antibiotics (CC, 2021).

Moreover, medication errors, lack of or low adherence rates to therapeutic protocols based on local sensitivities, self-medication, weak infection control systems, the use of antibiotic growth promoters in the agricultural livestock industry, wastewater pollution, and limited

incentives for new drug surveillance, research, and innovation can all contribute to AMR (Higuaita-Gutierrez et al., 2020, p. 2).

Consequently, when antibiotic resistance continues, this increases the risk of disease spread, severe illness, and even death. In addition, antibiotic-resistant bacteria can aggravate their associated community- and healthcare-acquired infections (WHO, 2021).

Knowledge of Antibiotic Use and Antimicrobial Resistance

Knowledge is “the fact or condition of knowing something with familiarity gained through experience or association” (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, n.d., para. 1). Knowledge of antibiotic use indicates a person’s understanding or familiarity with the idea of proper usage of antibiotics, which includes the correct practices and the related adverse effects when taken inappropriately. Furthermore, understanding AMR implies that they are aware of its negative impacts and that it can cause severe disruption to the body (Baddal et al., 2023).

Globally, AMR is one of the most concerning public health issues, so having enough knowledge is essential. Simegn et al. (2022) claim that awareness of the effects of AMR for health professionals helps prevent any infection, reducing the occurrence of AMR and promoting effective drug use. That is why it is important to use antibiotics only if needed to avoid harm caused by unnecessary antibiotic use and to combat AMR (CDC, 2022).

In 2020, the National Foundation for Infectious Disease (NFID) joined hands with the CDC (2022, para. 3) to introduce seven key facts people should know about antibiotics. First, antibiotics can save lives. When utilized properly, they function effectively and quickly. The advantages outweigh any adverse effects or the possibility of developing resistance. Second, using antibiotics is not always the best option. Although antibiotics may help some individuals, their persistent cough or cold would have resolved on its own in roughly the same amount of time. Third, antibiotics do not work on viruses. The flu, coronaviruses, and other viruses that cause colds, bronchitis, and runny noses cannot be treated with antibiotics. Fourthly, whereas all bacterial infections necessitate the use of antibiotics for treatment, antibiotics only function against bacteria. Antibiotics are not always necessary to treat all bacterial infections, including many sinus infections and some ear infections. Fifth, if a virus has infected the body, antibiotics will not help the illness. Even without treatment, respiratory viruses normally disappear in a week or two. Sixth, follow the directions on any prescribed antibiotics exactly. Consult a healthcare professional if experiencing any adverse effects, especially diarrhea, since this could indicate the presence of the pathogen *Clostridioides difficile* (*C. difficile*), which requires treatment. Lastly, antibiotics are crucial for treating illnesses that can lead to death, such as sepsis and some forms of pneumonia. This increases the significance of using antibiotics properly.

In the study of Tangcharoensathien et al. (2021, p. 6), “lack of knowledge and awareness on antimicrobial resistance can result in the irrational use of antibiotics, which is one of the major drivers of AMR.” Low knowledge of this matter may lead to misuse, overuse, and abuse. Several studies showed that a large population has a poor or moderate level of knowledge. Their low levels of knowledge subsequently led to their wrong beliefs and misconceptions about antibiotic use and AMR, causing improper practices. The improper practices toward antibiotics use increased AMR, which can potentially cause deleterious effects on people at any stage in life. It includes more extended hospitalization, costly alternative plans, frequent follow-up check-ups (CDC, 2020), and more severe side effects that can lead to death. It can also block the control of infectious diseases, affect the progress of healthcare, and damage the country’s economy (Research Institute for Tropical Medicine [RITM], 2016).

Attitude on Antibiotic Use and Antimicrobial Resistance

According to modern psychology, one’s attitude toward a behavior is generally determined by how positively or negatively one perceives oneself as performing it (BioMed Central, 2021). Attitude toward antibiotic use indicates how a person intakes antibiotics, positively or negatively.

Positive attitudes impose enough knowledge regarding the right and wrong use of antibiotics. It includes knowing that antibiotics should be prescribed by physicians, taking antibiotics with the correct dosage, not relying on the prescription of family and friends, not taking what is prescribed by others, and consulting a physician before buying antibiotics.

The physician prescribes to tell the pharmacist what medication a patient should take. According to Vilhena et al. (2021), the most significant benefit of taking medication exactly as prescribed is better health. Doctors prescribe medications to treat symptoms and to help manage or overcome certain health conditions. Thus, prescription medicines from doctors and pharmacies are regarded as safe.

Furthermore, taking antibiotics as prescribed by doctors comes with the correct dosage. According to Dignity Health (DH, 2018), taking antibiotics until the prescription is complete helps ensure that all illness-causing bacteria are killed or prevented from multiplying.

In addition, not relying on the prescriptions of family and friends imposes a great attitude toward medicines. Moreover, do not take antibiotics prescribed for someone else. It may delay the best treatment for the individual, make them even sicker, or cause severe side effects (CDC, 2022).

Lastly, consulting physicians is one of the factors of a positive attitude. A physician is a healthcare professional who has earned a medical degree and is clinically experienced (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). Thus, their assessment makes way for a better intake of antibiotics.

On the other hand, the prevalence of misuse and overuse of antibiotics due to people's negative attitudes toward their use is one of the factors in the increase of AMR. It includes self-medication, purchasing antibiotics without a prescription, not completing the entire course of antibiotics, sharing antibiotics, and keeping leftover antibiotics for future use.

Self-medication has traditionally been defined as "the taking of drugs, herbs or home remedies on one's initiative or on the advice of another person, without consulting a doctor" (Bennadi D., 2014, p. 3). Major problems related to self-medication are wastage of resources, increased resistance to pathogens, and severe health hazards such as adverse reactions and prolonged suffering (National Institute of Health, 2018). In the study conducted by Chua et al. (2021), the overall prevalence of self-medication with antibiotics among university students was 57.22%.

Additionally, researchers have warned about the growing problem of people taking antibiotics without a prescription. For a patient who stops treatment before the antibiotic cycle is over, the remaining bacteria can continue to multiply. It can also promote the spread of antibiotic-resistant properties among harmful bacteria (Mayo Clinic, 2022). In a multi-country survey by WHO (2015), nearly one-third (32%) of the population surveyed "believe that they should stop taking antibiotics when they feel better, rather than completing the prescribed course of treatment." In a study conducted by Lansang et al. (n.d.) in Manila, 66.3% of 1608 transactions involving purchases of antimicrobial agents were made without a prescription. Most were aminopenicillins, penicillin G, or V (40.0%).

Furthermore, sharing antibiotics and keeping leftover antibiotics for future use contributes to the increase of AMR. However, Alemnesh and Z Yohanes (2018) revealed that their respondents have positive attitudes toward antibiotic use. A present study, Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice toward Antibiotic Use among Harar City and Its Surrounding Community, Eastern Ethiopia, Alemnesh Jifar and Yohanes Ayele (2018) revealed a positive attitude toward the necessity of taking an entire course of the antibiotic's regimen (92.1%) and not using the leftover medicine (87.2%). This finding aligns with another study in which only 17% of respondents kept antibiotics in their homes for future use. However, it is far better than Namibian's study, in which 28.5% of users kept antibiotics in their homes for future use. A study that was conducted reported that 4580 (48.1%) kept antibiotics at home for children, and among those who had leftovers, it has 2891 (63.1%) that their leftovers came from previous prescriptions. Hence, people have a negative attitude towards antibiotic use.

Practice on Antibiotic Use

According to the CDC (2022), the correct practices on antibiotic use include taking them exactly as the doctor prescribes, sharing antibiotics with others as well as saving them for later is not advisable, and not taking antibiotics prescribed for someone else as this may delay the best treatment and can cause more severe side effects. MC (2022) states that if you do not take an antibiotic as prescribed, you may need to start treatment again later.

It should also be emphasized that an individual must complete the course of the antibiotic treatment even if symptoms improve (Felman, 2022). The reason behind this was explained by DH (2016), wherein when someone stops the treatment before the antibiotic cycle is over, it can make way for the remaining bacteria to multiply continuously. These remaining bacteria may have become resistant to the antibiotic, causing AMR, which can do more harm.

In recent years, several studies have found that most people have poor practices regarding antibiotic use, which further increases AMR worldwide. In the study of Aljayyousi et al. (2019) in Qatar, the respondents' primary inappropriate antibiotic use was using antibiotics without a prescription (82%), not completing the course of antibiotic treatment (45%), and buying antibiotics in pharmacies without a prescription (23%).

WHO (n.d., para. 7) defines self-medication as "the use of drugs to treat self-diagnosed disorders or symptoms, or the intermittent or continued use of a prescribed drug for chronic or recurrent disease or symptoms." Owusu-Ofori et al. (2021) gathered data that 56.2% of the respondents in Ghana had previously purchased antibiotics without a doctor's prescription, and 78.3% were satisfied with the effect of their self-medication. Likewise, a study conducted by Elmahi et al. (2022) in Sudan interpreted that 60.80% of the respondents self-medicated with antibiotics in the past 12 months. 38.1% of it was used to treat respiratory tract infections and 30.4% was for cough. Another similar study was performed in Malaysia by Haque et al. (2019), where they reported that 39.3% of the respondents self-medicate. Most of the antibiotics used were penicillin, doxycycline, and clarithromycin.

The Philippines is one of the countries that have the highest rates of antibiotic sharing and misuse worldwide (Tagum-Briones et al., 2023). In the study of Barber et al. (2016), a result was gathered indicating that most respondents (78%) admitted having shared antibiotics in their lifetime. Furthermore, antibiotics are widely available in sari-sari stores (60%), and an entire course of antibiotics is commonly unavailable (68%). It was further supported by the study of Robredo et al. (2022), wherein they reported that self-medication is widespread in the country, with an occurrence of 31-66%.

Intaking antibiotics improperly will lead not only to common side effects like digestive problems, fungal infections, urinary tract infections (UTI), drug interaction, photosensitivity, and staining but will also lead to severe side effects. Misuse of antibiotics might lead to more severe, serious, and life-threatening side effects or, worse, long-term side effects. These severe side effects include Anaphylaxis, a highly severe allergic reaction, and clostridium difficile-induced colitis is a bacterium that infects the intestines, specifically the large intestines, causing intestinal inflammation, antibiotic resistance, and kidney disease. As for the long-term side

effects, these include cardiovascular disease and different types of cancer (Huizen, J, n.d.).

Most of the studies revealed in this section emphasized that a massive population has poor to moderate knowledge, attitude, and practice on antibiotic use and AMR. That means only a tiny population possesses good knowledge, attitude, and practice on antibiotic use and AMR. Despite the importance of assessing people's perception and practice regarding antibiotics, which is the main contributing factor to the increase of AMR worldwide, most of these studies were conducted in universities and hospitals where the respondents were already exposed to the concept of antibiotics and AMR. However, less attention has been paid to common citizens outside the medical field who may or may not be aware of the concept of antibiotics and AMR.

This study determined the knowledge, attitude, and practice on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance among tenants of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. Therefore, the study's result can be the basis for intervention and creating an action plan to broaden the community's knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding antibiotics and their proper use to help combat the dangerous, prevalent global health issue of AMR.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the knowledge, attitude, and practice on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance among tenants of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. Specifically, the study sought the answer of the following questions:

1. What is the level of knowledge of the tenants of Bayombong on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance?
2. What is the attitude of the tenants of Bayombong on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance?
3. What are the practices of the tenants of Bayombong on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance?
4. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' knowledge on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance when grouped according to:
 - 4.1. age;
 - 4.2. educational attainment; and
 - 4.3. socio-economic status?
5. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' attitude on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance when grouped according to:
 - 5.1. age;
 - 5.2. educational attainment; and
 - 5.3. socio-economic status?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the knowledge of the respondents and their practice toward the use of antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the attitude of the respondents and their practice toward the use of antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized both qualitative and quantitative methods. A descriptive comparative-correlational design was used in the quantitative section of the study. A descriptive approach was applied to determine the knowledge and attitude on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance among tenants in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, which may provide a basis for intervention. A comparative approach was used to explain, describe, and interpret the significant differences in the participants' knowledge and attitude on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance when grouped according to their profiles. On the other hand, a correlational approach was used to examine if there was a significant relationship and the extent of the relationship between knowledge and practice, as well as the relationship between attitude and practice. The data from the quantitative method was presented in numerical and tabular form and was correlated to the degree of knowledge, attitude, and practice on antibiotic use and antibiotic resistance. Aside from that, the qualitative method was also used for the practice section to understand better the respondents' knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance.

Participants

The study gathered significant data from individuals temporarily residing in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, specifically tenants. The study includes those aged 18 and above who are temporarily living or are renters in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The participants' socio-demographics were grouped according to age, educational attainment, and socio-economic status.

The sampling technique that was used for this study is purposive quota sampling. Purposive sampling was utilized since the respondents are the tenants living in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. It suggests that the study only considers the tenants from the population in which they were selected. On the other hand, quota sampling was applied because this study needs to meet a certain quota. Moreover, there is no specific population of tenants in Bayombong, so there is no approximation as to the suitable sample size. Hence, the use of quota sampling. The minimum target respondents of the study are at least 200 participants, which was attained. The participants were

evaluated regarding their levels of knowledge, attitude, and practice on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance concerning their socio-demographic profile.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of Respondents*

<i>Profile Variable</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Age Group		
18-29 years old	135	67.50%
29-39 years old	38	19.00%
40-49 years old	20	10.00%
50-59 years old	5	2.50%
60 years old and above	2	1.00%
Total	200	100%
Educational Attainment		
Elementary Undergraduate	0	0%
Elementary Graduate	0	0%
High School Undergraduate	7	3.50%
High School Graduate	21	10.50%
College Undergraduate	107	53.50%
College Graduate	65	32.50%
Others	0	0%
Total	200	100%
Socio-economic Status		
<Php 11,000	84	42.00%
Php 11,000- Php 21,999	28	14.00%
Php 22,000- Php 43,999	51	25.50%
Php 44,000- Php 76,999	27	13.50%
Php 77,000- Php 131,999	4	2.00%
Php 132,000- Php 219,999	3	1.50%
>Php 220,000	3	1.50%
Total	200	100%

Table 4 presents the summary of the frequency and percentage count of the demographic profile of the respondents. A total of 200 respondents agreed to participate in the study. As can be seen, more than half of the respondents ranges from 18-29 years old, followed by nearly 20% are in the age bracket of 30-39 years old, 10% are in the age bracket of 40-49 years old, 2.5% are in the age bracket of 50-59 years old, and 1% are 60 years old and above. As can be seen, the frequency of 18-29 years old is high, meaning that most of the respondents belong to this age bracket.

Meanwhile, 107 (53.5%) of the respondents are currently college undergraduates, 65 (32.5%) are college graduates, 21 (10.5%) are high school graduates, 7 (3.5%) are high school undergraduates, while elementary undergraduate, elementary graduate, and others have 0 (0%) respondents. It implies that the majority of the respondents are college undergraduates. However, it should also be taken into consideration that there are no participants who represent the elementary undergraduate and elementary graduate population. Thus, it is reasonable to conclude that these educational attainment groups are excluded from the study.

Lastly, the table also shows that 84 (42%) respondents have a monthly income of less than Php 11, 000, 51 (25.5%) has Php 22,000-Php 43,999, 28 (14%) has Php 11,000- Php 21,999, 27 (13.5%) are Php 44,000- Php 76,999, 4 (2%) has Php 77,000- Php 131,999, while both Php 132,000- Php 219,999 and more than Php 220,000 has a percentage of 1.5% or three respondents. As can be seen, nearly half of the respondents have a monthly income of less than Php 11,000. Overall, the results indicate that most of the survey respondents are young adults from low-income households.

Instruments

The collection of data for the study was primarily facilitated through a survey questionnaire. It was adapted and modified from a research study entitled Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices of Antimicrobial Uses and Resistance Among Public University Students in Bangladesh conducted by Marzan et al. (2021).

The questionnaire is written in English with a Filipino translation so that the questions can be understood easily, and the respondents can give accurate answers. It was divided into two parts.

The first part of the questionnaire included the necessary information regarding the profile of the respondents. Age, educational attainment, and socio-economic status were asked through a checkbox type of question, and the respondents answered it by placing checkmarks on what category they belong.

The second part consists of questions that were used to determine the respondents' knowledge, attitude, and practices on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. It was further divided into three categories. The first category measures the level of knowledge of the respondents in regards to antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance, which consists of thirteen-item statements that are answerable by

True or False, which measures the respondent's correct and incorrect responses to the statement. The second category measures the attitude of the respondents regarding antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance, which consists of twenty-item statements on a 4-point Likert Scale measuring the respondents' degree of agreement or disagreement with the statement. Specifically, "4 as strongly agree", "3 as agree", "2 as disagree", and "1 as strongly disagree". The third category evaluated the respondents' practices and habits regarding antibiotic use and their adherence to dosing and treatment courses using three-item checkbox type of questions.

Table 2. *Result of Reliability Test*

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.789	.789	20

The table shows the reliability statistic. Based on the table, Cronbach's alpha is equal to 0.789. Its internal consistency is equivalent to acceptable ($0.8 \geq \alpha \geq 0.7$). Therefore, the questionnaire is reliable.

Procedure

An adapted questionnaire from the study of Marzan et al. (2021) was modified and altered by the researchers to suit the significance and the target respondents of the study. It underwent content validation and was checked by the research adviser. After finalizing the questionnaire that was utilized in this study, it underwent pilot testing for reliability test first before being reproduced into hard copies. After that, the questionnaires were physically distributed to the respondents in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. But before the respondents answer the questionnaire, the researchers sought their consent. The survey questionnaires were then collected and tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted. Lastly, after a thorough interpretation, the researchers came up with conclusions, suggestions, and recommendations to inform the readers about the findings and results of the study.

Data Analysis

This study applied both quantitative and qualitative methods. Specifically, the descriptive-comparative-correlational design was used in the quantitative section of the study. Hence, to treat the data gathered, the following tools and techniques were used:

The demographic profile of the respondents, specifically the age, educational attainment, and socio-economic status, were evaluated using descriptive statistics, specifically the frequency count and percentage distribution.

The knowledge of the respondents in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya in terms of antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance were assessed through a questionnaire. The mean scores and standard deviation of Bloom's cutoff point were computed to determine the knowledge of the respondents on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. Table 3 shows the mean score and its interpretation.

The mean scores and standard deviation of the 4-point Likert scale were computed to determine the attitude of the respondents toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. The equal interval was also utilized since this type of scale produces an accurate and valid analysis. Table 4 shows the mean score range and its interpretation.

The practice of the respondents on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance were evaluated using the same statistical treatment used for the profile, the frequency count, and the percentage distribution.

When grouped according to age, educational attainment, and socio-economic status, statistical tools, specifically the analysis of variance (ANOVA), were used in determining the significant difference in knowledge, attitude, and practice on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance.

The significant relationship between knowledge and practices and the significant relationship between attitude and practices were determined using the Pearson Correlation.

Table 3. *Bloom Scale cut-off Interpretation for Level of Knowledge*

Mean Score	Interpretation
80% - 100%	Good
60% - 79.9%	Moderate
Below 60%	Poor

Table 4. *Likert Scale Interpretation for Attitude*

Mean Score	Interpretation
3.50-4.00	Highly Negative
2.50-3.49	Negative
1.50-2.49	Positive

1.00-1.49 Highly Positive

Ethical Considerations

The researchers of this study had observed ethical considerations. The researchers submitted the study to the Saint Mary’s University Research Ethics Board.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Confidentiality and Data Protection

The researchers abided by the “Data Privacy Act of 2012” or the Republic Act 10173, where the anonymity of the respondents will be strictly kept to protect sensitive information from malicious use. All information the researchers collected was kept confidential and stored in a Google Drive file that only the researchers can access. Similarly, the file keeper handled the physical copies of information and answered questionnaires, which only the researchers had access. Upon request of the board of panelists, the researcher may grant access to the file for verification. Lastly, once the study is published, the researchers will present the data that are analyzed and interpreted to ensure the anonymity of the respondents. Then they will delete all existing files.

Management of Vulnerability

Vulnerable populations were not excluded from the study. Instead, the researchers provided them with appropriate support to help them make informed decisions about participating in the study. If they agreed, the researchers guided them in answering the questions.

Risk/Benefit Ratio

As community-based research, it involves engaging with people in their own homes. It potentially raises issues regarding intrusion and confidentiality. Hence, the researchers considered and ensured the anonymity and autonomy of the respondents. With their utmost participation, the study’s findings benefit the whole community with the actions that will be implemented based on this study.

Informed Consents

The researchers considered the freedom of the respondents throughout as they were presented with their choice to reject or participate in the study through informed consent.

Terms of Reference

The hard copy of this study is owned by Saint Mary’s University-Senior High School. The researchers in this study remains to be the owners and authors of the work.

Results and Discussion

The section on research results and discussion presents an in-depth discussion of the analyzed results from the gathered data. This chapter discusses the level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the respondents toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance, the differences in the knowledge and attitudes among the independent variables, and the relationship between knowledge and practices, as well as the relationship between attitudes and practices of the respondents.

Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices

This section presents the level of knowledge, attitude, and practices of the respondents included in the study. The level of knowledge was divided into three rows that shows the different levels of knowledge and the corresponding frequency count and percentage distribution of each level. Then, the level of attitude was evaluated through the respondents’ attitude scores in the 4-point Likert Scale part of the survey questionnaire by presenting the standard deviation and interpreting the mean scores. Lastly, the practices were evaluated and presented using the frequency count and percentage distribution.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Counts of the Respondents’ Level of Knowledge

<i>Level of Knowledge</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Good	92	46.0%
Moderate	81	40.5%
Poor	27	13.5%
Total	200	100.0%

**Legend: Knowledge: 80% - 100% = Good; 60% - 79.9% = Moderate; Below 60% = Poor*

Table 5 shows the tenants' level of knowledge regarding antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. As can be seen, out of 200 respondents, almost half of the sample size has a good level of knowledge, followed by nearly 41% of the respondents who gained a moderate level of knowledge, and almost 14% of the respondents had a poor level of knowledge. It implies that a large population has

a good level of knowledge. It also means that most respondents are highly knowledgeable regarding the proper utilization of antibiotics. Hence, they are less likely to misuse antibiotics and more likely to avoid exposure to antimicrobial resistance. However, it should be noted that a good level of knowledge is closely followed by nearly half the population with moderate knowledge. It may imply that half of the respondents have average and inadequate knowledge and understanding of antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance. Despite possessing good knowledge of most of the respondents, there is a need to note that almost 14% of the respondents have poor knowledge and are likely to be prone to misuse, overuse, and abuse of antibiotics. It can be assumed that they are most likely to develop antimicrobial resistance and be exposed to its side effects, such as nausea, diarrhea, vomiting, indigestion, bloating, loss of appetite, and stomach pain (Felman, 2022). A study by Waaseth et al. (2019) mentioned that despite a high level of knowledge of antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance, gaps still occur. Furthermore, the CDC (2020) mentioned that improper utilization of antibiotics has led to increased antimicrobial resistance, which can harm people at any stage of life.

Table 6. Score of the Respondents in the Knowledge Section (n=200)

Statements	Expected Ideal Response	Correct	Incorrect
Antibiotics are a type of medicine that fight infection. (Ang antibiotics ay isang uri ng gamot na panlaban sa impeksiyon.)	True	191 (95.5%)	9 (4.5%)
Antibiotics are effective in the treatment of bacterial infections. (Ang antibiotics ay epektibo sa paggamot ng impeksyon na dulot ng bacteria.)	True	195 (97.5%)	5 (2.5%)
Antibiotics are effective in the treatment of viral infections. (Ang antibiotics ay epektibo sa paggamot ng impeksyon na dulot ng virus.)	False	87 (43.5%)	113 (56.5%)
Antibiotics are effective for the treatment of both bacterial and viral infections. (Ang antibiotics ay epektibo sa parehong impeksyon na dulot ng bacteria at virus.)	False	87 (43.5%)	113 (56.5%)
Antibiotics can only be purchased using a prescription. (Ang antibiotics ay nabibili lamang kapag may reseta.)	True	163 (81.5%)	37 (18.5%)
The use of antibiotics will speed up the recovery from a cold, and cough. (Ang paggamit ng antibiotics ay magpapabilis sa paggaling mula sa sipon, at ubo.)	False	51 (25.5%)	149 (74.5%)
Taking antibiotics has associated side effects. (Ang pag-inom ng antibiotics ay may kaakibat ng mga side effect.)	True	187 (93.5%)	13 (6.5%)
Some side effects or risks of antibiotic use include diarrhea, colitis, and allergies. (Ang ilan sa side effects o panganib ng paggamit ng antibiotic ay pagtatae, colitis, at allergies.)	True	156 (78%)	44 (22%)
Antibiotic resistance is the loss of activity of an antibiotic. (Antibiotic resistance ay ang pagkawala ng aktibidad ng isang antibiotic.)	True	150 (75%)	50 (25%)
Consumption of antibiotics without a physician's prescription can contribute to antibiotic resistance. (Ang pagkonsumo ng mga antibiotic na walang reseta ng doktor ay maaaring magbigay ng dahilan sa pagkawala ng bisa ng antibiotic.)	True	157 (78.5%)	43 (21.5%)
Antibiotic resistance can be caused by the overuse of antibiotics. (Ang pagkawalang bisa ng antibiotic ay maaring sanhi ng labis na paggamit nito.)	True	168 (84%)	32 (16%)
Healthy people can carry antibiotic-resistant bacteria. (Ang mga taong may malakas na pangangatawan ay maaaring magkaroon ng mga bacteria na hindi malalabanan ng antibiotic.)	True	111 (55.5%)	89 (44.5%)
Antibiotic-resistant bacteria can spread from person to person. (Ang bacteria na hindi malalabanan ng antibiotic ay maaaring makahawa mula sa isang tao papunta sa isa pa.)	True	115 (57.5%)	85 (42.5%)

Table 6 summarizes the respondents' responses to each statement of the survey questionnaire. As can be seen, almost 100% of the respondents have correctly identified that antibiotics are a type of medicine that fights infection. However, an alarmingly large population of almost 60% of the respondents believe antibiotics are effective for treating bacterial and viral infections. This misconception is seen in the results, which show that about 75% of the respondents believe antibiotics can speed up recovery from a cough or cold.

Regarding antibiotic resistance, it was shown that 25% of the respondents are not knowledgeable about the condition where antibiotics lose their effectiveness. With regard to its purchase, about 82% of the respondents have correctly identified that antibiotics can only be purchased with a physician's prescription. However, it is essential to note that there is still a significant minority of people (18.5%) who believe otherwise. This result aligns with the almost 80% of respondents who have correctly identified that the consumption of antibiotics without a physician's prescription can contribute to antibiotic resistance. Likewise, it is noteworthy that there is still a minority of the population (21.5%) who are not knowledgeable about it. Moreover, there is a significant 16% of respondents who are not knowledgeable that one of the consequences of antibiotic overuse is antibiotic resistance.

Lastly, the results have shown that nearly half of the population is unaware that healthy people can carry antibiotic-resistant bacteria, nor can these bacteria spread from person to person.

The first results indicate that the respondents have a basic understanding of antibiotics and their uses given that they have correctly identified antibiotics as a medicine used to fight infections. It is a good start, as this particular piece of knowledge is the prerequisite in learning and identifying the proper uses of antibiotics. However, although the respondents know that antibiotics are used to treat infections, they are not knowledgeable about what type of infections it can treat. Hence, they are at risk of antibiotic resistance since they are not aware of the proper intake of antibiotics and also hold a misconception that antibiotics can prevent viral infection. It is alarming since it is considered dangerous as it can lead to people using antibiotics unnecessarily, which increases the chance of antimicrobial resistance.

The result regarding antibiotic resistance signifies that an alarming or significant percentage of the population needs to be educated about this issue. Although 25% is a small population based on the sample size, considering the global population, it encompasses roughly two billion people. With that, educating people about medicines, particularly antibiotics, is needed since it affects billions of people globally. On the other hand, the results regarding its purchase indicate that some of the population is unaware that antibiotics should only be purchased using a prescription. It can be assumed that they believe that antibiotics can be purchased without a prescription because they were able to acquire such antibiotics without a prescription during their lifetime. Moreover, without proper knowledge regarding the situation, people can use antibiotics freely because they are unaware of the side effects, particularly antibiotic resistance, of misusing antibiotics. Hence, it is essential to be knowledgeable about this fact as it can help people make sound decisions with the proper usage of antibiotics.

Lastly, the result implies that the respondents are unaware that antibiotic-resistant bacteria can affect anyone at any stage of life, and even the healthiest cannot prevent it. This perception can lead to people disregarding the seriousness of the issue because they believe there is little to no chance of acquiring the said bacteria if they are healthy. Similarly, not having enough knowledge about these bacteria may lead to their spread since people are unaware that they are contagious, and they may accidentally spread the bacteria to other people.

Similar to the survey conducted by Muflih et al. (2021), most respondents correctly identified antibiotics as a medicine that fights infection. Moreover, over half of the respondents (51.1%) in the study of Shatla et al. (2020) likewise believe that antibiotics effectively treat viral infections. However, it was shown that only 27.9% of the respondents of Shrestha in their study in 2019 were aware that antibiotics are ineffective against common symptoms. The results of this study align with theirs, wherein about 75% of the respondents are not knowledgeable about it. Regarding antibiotic resistance, the results also align with the same study of Shrestha, which states that most of their respondents have good knowledge about the condition where antibiotics lose their effectiveness since most respondents were students of health-related programs.

On the other hand, a study by Sitotaw and Philipos (2023) reported that 40.7% of respondents disagreed that antibiotics can only be purchased using a prescription. It suggests that their respondents are unaware that non-prescription antibiotics are illegal and unprofessional practices and are more at risk of antibiotic resistance, which does not align with the result of this study. In contrast with the results, the study by Marzan (2020) found that 88.5% of the respondents presented good knowledge by agreeing that the consumption of antibiotics without a physician's prescription can contribute to antibiotic resistance since the majority of his respondents belong to the health-related programs and are exposed to basic knowledge of health topics.

Like Marzan's study, 79.6% of his respondents know that overuse of antibiotics may lead to antibiotic resistance. However, in a study conducted by Barchitta (2021), the majority of the respondents (88%) are sensible that antimicrobial resistance is anyone's victim, which is in contrast with the result of this study. Nevertheless, he also reported that 92% of his respondents were members of the healthcare team and correctly answered that antibiotic-resistant bacteria can spread to other people, which is in line with the result of this study.

Table 7. Attitude of the Respondents Toward Antibiotic Use and Antimicrobial Resistance

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
If I catch a cold, I ask for an antibiotic prescription to prevent my symptoms from getting worse. (Kapag nagka sipon ako, humihingi ako ng reseta ng antibiotic para maiwasang lumala ang mga sintomas.)	2.595	1.076	Negative
I believe that antibiotics cure my cold faster. (Naniniwala ako na mas mabilis na nalulunasan ng antibiotic ang sipon ko.)	2.710	1.054	Negative
I take leftover antibiotics when I have similar flu symptoms. (Umiinom ako ng mga tirang antibiotic kapag mayroon akong mga sintomas ng trangkaso.)	2.195	1.142	Positive
I prefer a shot of oral medicine if antibiotics are needed. (Mas gusto kong inumin ang gamot na antibiotics kung kailangan.)	2.005	0.985	Positive
I would stop taking the prescribed antibiotics if I got better. (Nihihinto ko ang pag-inom ng mga ni resetang antibiotic kapag ako ay gumaling.)	2.820	1.031	Negative
I think physicians often prescribe antibiotics unnecessarily.	1.790	0.933	Positive

(Sa tingin ko ang mga doktor ay madalas na nagre-reseta ng mga antibiotic nang hindi kinakailangan.)			
I believe that antibiotic resistance is increasing. (Naniniwala ako na tumataas ang bilang ng antibiotic resistance.)	2.015	0.836	Positive
I think we should be more concerned regarding antibiotic consumption.	1.425	0.661	Highly Positive
(Sa tingin ko, nararapat na mas maging mabahala tayo tungkol sa paggamit ng antibiotic.)			
I keep antibiotics at home for future use because I want to save money.	2.560	1.012	Negative
(Nag-iimbak ako ng mga antibiotics sa bahay para magamit sa hinaharap dahil gusto kong makatipid.)			
Enough knowledge should be generated to prevent antibiotic resistance.	1.475	0.729	Highly Positive
(Sapat na kaalaman ang dapat mabuo upang maiwasan ang pagkawala ng bisa ng antibiotic.)			
I would rather take an antibiotic that may not be needed than wait to see if I get better without it.	2.205	1.020	Positive
(Mas gugustuhin kong uminom ng antibiotic na maaaring hindi na kailangan kaysa maghintay kung gagaling ako nang wala ito.)			
If I expect to receive an antibiotic but was not able to receive it, I am less satisfied with a doctor's visit.	2.175	1.005	Positive
(Kapag inaasahan kong makakatanggap ako ng antibiotic pero hindi ko iyon natanggap, hindi ako nasisiyahan sa pagbisita ng doktor.)			
If a doctor does not prescribe an antibiotic when I think one is needed, I will go to another doctor. (Kung ang doktor ay hindi nagre-reseta ng antibiotic na sa tingin ko ay kailangan ko, ako ay pupunta sa ibang doktor.)	2.440	1.040	Positive
I prefer to be able to buy antibiotics from the pharmacy without a prescription. (Mas gusto kong makabili ng antibiotic sa botika nang walang reseta.)	2.090	1.062	Positive
If I had some antibiotic pills left, I would use them with confidence for the following similar symptoms.	2.305	1.018	Positive
(Kung mayroon akong ilang tabletas ng antibiotic na natitira, gagamitin ko ang mga ito nang may lakas ng loob para sa mga sumusunod na katulad na sintomas.)			
It is good to complete the course of treatment with antibiotics even if I feel better. (Mainam na kumpletuhin ang kurso ng paggamot ng antibiotic kapag bumuti na ang pakiramdam ko.)	1.870	0.931	Positive
Even if the antibiotic has expired, I can still use it for up to one year. (Kahit na ang antibiotic ay nag-expire na, ang mga antibiotic ay maaari pa ring gamitin nang hanggang sa isang taon)	1.615	0.975	Positive
It is okay to use antibiotics that were given by a friend or family member if they were used to treat the same illness. (Ayos lang na gamitin ang antibiotics na bigay ng kaibigan o miyembro ng pamilya kung ginamit ito sa panlunas ng parehong sakit.)	2.250	1.069	Positive
Non-prescribed antibiotics sale should be prohibited. (Dapat ipagbawal ang pagbebenta ng mga hindi iniresetang antibiotic.)	1.760	1.024	Positive
When someone is trying to self-medicate, I try to persuade them not to do it. (Kapag sinusubukan ng isang tao na gamutin ang sarili, sinisikap kong hikayatin silang huwag gawin ito.)	2.065	1.008	Positive
	Average	2.118	0.465
			Positive

*Legend: Attitude: 3.50 – 4.00 (Highly Negative), 2.50 – 3.49 (Negative), 1.50 – 2.49 (Positive), 1.00 – 1.49 (Highly Positive)

Table 7 summarizes the mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation of the respondents' responses to each of the items from the survey questionnaire. As can be seen, the respondents' overall attitudes were positive, with a mean of 2.118. However, there is still a need to address some attitudes that were reported to be negative based on the respondents' answers. The results show that the general population believes in and has used antibiotics to cure colds faster and to prevent symptoms from worsening, which gained a mean of 2.595 and 2.710, respectively.

Regarding the course of antibiotic use, the results have shown that the average person in the study has conformed to the practice of stopping the antibiotic courses when someone feels better, generating a negative attitude ($m=2.820$). However, the result for this item does not coincide with the positive attitude ($m=1.870$) gained by the respondents in item 16, where the majority of them agreed that it is good to complete the course of antibiotics even if someone feels better before the course is finished.

Further, results found the positive attitude of the respondents when it comes to leftover antibiotics. It has shown that most respondents disagree with the statements of taking leftover antibiotics when experiencing similar flu symptoms and using them confidently for the following similar symptoms, which gained a mean of 2.195 and 2.305, respectively. However, one of the significant results contradicts the latter's results wherein people tend to store antibiotics for future use to save money since most respondents agreed to the statement, gaining a mean of 2.560.

On the positive side, the study's general population strongly agreed that people should be more concerned regarding antibiotic consumption and that generating enough knowledge should be done to combat antibiotic resistance, gaining a mean of 1.425 and 1.475,

respectively.

Furthermore, individual's doctor satisfaction was found to be positive attitudes. It can be seen in the results that the majority of the respondents disagreed with the statements of unnecessary prescription of antibiotics by physicians, being unsatisfied with a doctor's visit if antibiotics were not received, and visiting another doctor if the previous doctor did not prescribe an antibiotic, gaining a mean of 1.790, 2.175, and 2.440, respectively.

In terms of self-medication, the results show that most respondents disagreed with buying antibiotics without a prescription; instead, they agreed to the prohibition of non-prescribed antibiotics sales, garnering the means of 2.090 and 1.760, respectively. It was also presented that the respondents have a highly positive attitude toward dissuading people trying to self-medicate, with a mean of 2.065. In relation, the respondents have likewise shown positive attitudes toward the statements of taking expired antibiotics and using antibiotics that a friend or family gave. It means the respondents disagreed with these statements, having garnered the mean scores of 1.615 and 2.250, respectively.

The general attitude shown by the respondents was positive. However, a negative attitude towards antibiotics still prevails. One of which is the misconception of its effectiveness in curing colds and preventing symptoms from worsening, to which the respondents have reported using antibiotics for those purposes. These particular attitudes suggest that people are unaware of the dangers of antibiotic misuse since they are not knowledgeable that antibiotics should not be used to treat viral infections like colds. With this lack of awareness resulting in a negative attitude, it can be implied that there is a chance that people are more likely to practice and misuse antibiotics, which includes using them as a treatment for colds. The incorrect use of antibiotics contributes to the increase of antibiotic and antimicrobial resistance, which are known to be a dangerous health issue that affects people at any stage of life.

One of the major misconceptions and practices that lead to antimicrobial resistance is stopping the course of antibiotics when someone feels better. The result suggests that people are not fully aware and were not appropriately oriented by physicians when they were given prescriptions about antibiotics, specifically what to do and what not to do, unless people are acquiring antibiotics without the prescription and guidance of a physician. Therefore, people are unaware of the risks and dangers stemming from incomplete doses of antibiotics. Besides, the latter's result implies that although people know that antibiotic courses should be finished regardless of whether someone feels better, they are not practicing its proper use.

Regarding leftover antibiotics, although one of the results has shown that respondents' attitudes were positive, there is a need to note that people still have the tendency to store antibiotics for future purposes. This particular attitude is considered negative since antibiotics are not meant to be stored for the possibility of acquiring the same illness in the future. Acquiring the same illness in the future does not automatically mean that the microorganisms that caused that disease are identical to the previous one. Intaking the same antibiotics leads to the adaptation of microorganisms, making them resistant to that particular antibiotic, which leads to the treatment being ineffective. Hence, it is advised to stop storing leftover antibiotics.

The results regarding antibiotic consumption and generating enough knowledge signify that people are willing to be oriented and knowledgeable about this issue, contributing to combatting the global health issue of antimicrobial resistance. The results presented that these are highly positive attitudes as they show the willingness of the community to be educated regarding antibiotic consumption and its resistance.

Regarding doctor satisfaction, the results have shown that the respondents have positive feedback toward doctors' performances. The results imply that the study's general population is satisfied and believes a doctor's diagnosis regarding their health. It further suggests that patients do not tend to be insistent on the intake of antibiotics; instead, they believe a professional's opinion and diagnosis. It is considered a good attitude since understanding and following a professional's opinion, especially that of a health practitioner, regarding health matters can indicate that a person is less likely to self-medicate. In connection, the respondents' attitudes toward self-medication were positive. These suggest that the study's general population positively understands self-medication. It shows that individuals are encouraging other people not to self-medicate. Instead, they are likely encouraging them to visit a physician for a professional's diagnosis. In a nutshell, they know that self-medication is not recommended and can even cause much more deleterious effects on someone's health.

The results coincide with the findings of Zaidi et al. (2020), where 25.7% believed that taking antibiotics for cold symptoms could help them recover faster, while 39.6% expected antibiotics to be prescribed for common cold symptoms. Similarly, Nepal et al. (2019) stated that nearly half (47.7%) believed antibiotics helped them get better more quickly if they had a fever. In the same way, the study of Karuniawati et al. (2021) stated that 50% of respondents had considered stopping the intake of prescribed antibiotics as soon as symptoms had disappeared, which resulted in a negative attitude, supporting this study's findings. Likewise, the results of this study agree with the study of Dejene et al. (2022), which indicated that 50% of the respondents agreed with the statement that it is good to complete the course of treatment with antibiotics when they feel better.

Correspondingly, the study by Li et al. (2020) indicated that 34.9% of the participants disagreed with saving up leftover antibiotics and then used them for similar symptoms. Also, in the study by Pogurschi et al. (2022), the percentage of respondents who confidently used remaining antibiotics for recurrent similar symptoms was 21.19%, while the vast majority, 67.58%, disagreed. Likewise, they found that over 57.73% of the respondents agree on keeping antibiotics at home for future use, which is all in line with the results of

this study.

Similar to the results, the study by Marzan et al. (2020) presented that 97.5% of students agreed with the statement of being more cautious regarding the intake of antibiotics. Likewise, the study of Awad et al. (2015) shows that almost 47% of participants had high knowledge regarding antibiotic action, use, safety, and resistance.

Regarding doctor satisfaction, it is similar to the study of Alnasser et al. (2021), which shows that over 91.87% of the participants believed doctors should not give antibiotics when unnecessary. Nepal et al. (2019) also reported that most respondents (61.8%) were not less satisfied with a doctor's visit if they did not receive an antibiotic. In contrast, the study by Nepal et al. shows that the majority (88.2%) of the respondents indicated they would go to another doctor if not prescribed an antibiotic when they thought one was needed. Analogously, the study by Jifar and Ayele (2018) shows that over 37.3% of respondents disagree with the statement that they prefer to be able to buy antibiotics from the pharmacy without a prescription. Likewise, the study by Higuaita-Gutiérrez et al. (2020) shows that over 60% of respondents agree that non-prescribed antibiotic sales should be prohibited.

The study by Bert et al. (2022) shows that 74% of the participants would prefer not to self-medicate without a physician's prescription. Similarly, the study by Pogurschi et al. (2022) revealed that 76.78% of the respondents disagreed with the statement of using expired antibiotics. Additionally, the study by Muflih et al. (2021) shows that 82.2% of the respondents felt that using antibiotics given to them by a friend or family member was unacceptable. All of the results of the previous studies support this study's findings.

Table 8. Frequency and Percentage of Respondents Based on their Practice of Taking Antibiotics

<i>Practices</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
How do you generally take antibiotics?		
Physician's prescription	168	84%
Self-medication	45	22.5%
Suggested by friends or relatives	36	18%
According to the previous prescription	50	25%
Others	0	0%
When do you generally take antibiotics?		
Fever	100	50%
Cough or cold	100	50%
Any kind of pain	32	16%
Surgery	54	27%
Wound or fracture	53	26.5%
Skin lesions or pustules	20	10%
Urine infection	76	38%
Ear infection	43	21.5%
Gastroenteritis	12	6%
Others	10	5%
Do you fail to complete the doses of antibiotics? If yes, what are the causes of incomplete medication?		
Stop taking antibiotics when I feel better	106	53%
Stop taking antibiotics when I face an allergic reaction	77	38.5%
Usually do not complete the course of antibiotics	33	16.5%
Stop taking when gastrointestinal discomforts occur	47	23.5%
Forget to take medicine properly	62	31%
Others	2	1%

Table 8 presents the summary of the respondents' practices regarding taking antibiotics. From a sample of 200 respondents, 168 or 84% of the respondents rely on the physician's prescription when taking antibiotics. However, it should also be noted that of the 200 respondents, 50 (25%) rely on their previous prescription, 45 (22.5%) have self-medicated, and 36 (18%) take antibiotics through the suggestions of friends or relatives. Next, to recover from various illnesses, 100 (50%) respondents reported taking antibiotics to recover from fever, and another 100 (50%) respondents took antibiotics to cure cough or cold. Lastly, 106 (53%) respondents stop taking antibiotics when they feel better. Furthermore, 77 (38.5%) respondents failed to complete the doses of antibiotics when they faced an allergic reaction. The results imply that most respondents have good practice regarding the intake of antibiotics, which are supposed to be prescribed by a physician. However, it must also be pointed out that more than half of the sample population has self-medicated, taken antibiotics that friends or relatives suggest, and according to previous prescriptions. All of these are considered poor practices in the intake of antibiotics. Thus, the good practices of the respondents are not far off from their poor practices.

The following result suggests that the respondents generally take antibiotics when they have common diseases such as fever, cough, or cold. The result indicates that the respondents are unaware that antibiotics are only effective in treating bacterial infections and not for viral infections such as fever, cough, and colds caused by viruses. It holds the highest percentage, and it is alarming since antibiotics should not be used to cure viral diseases, including these.

Lastly, the results signify that a large population does not conform to the good practices on the intake of antibiotics since antibiotic courses should be completed regardless of whether someone feels better even before the course is finished. It is important not to stop the doses of antibiotics; instead, consult with the doctor first before discontinuing them (Felman, 2023). In the study of Karuniawati et al. (2021), the result found that 41% of the respondents sometimes buy antibiotics without a physician's prescription. Moreover, 35% of their respondents admitted having recommended their family members antibiotics when sick. Additionally, Ateshim et al. (2019) discovered that self-medication-seeking behavior was prevalent among the 580 participants. Likewise, the study by Karuniawati et al. (2019) reported that 43% of the respondents took antibiotics to speed up their recovery from a cold. Furthermore, 60% of the respondents have admitted to taking antibiotics to speed up recovery from various illnesses (Halim, 2018). Lastly, the result of the study coincides with the study of Aljaysousi et al. (2019), where 45% of the respondents are not completing the course of antibiotic treatment.

Differences in the Level of Knowledge of the Respondents Based on Demographic Profile

The analysis and interpretation of the difference in the respondents' knowledge when grouped according to their profile is based on the p-value of the ANOVA. Furthermore, determining which group has better knowledge was based on the mean differences from the multiple comparison test. Specifically, the results of the multiple comparison tests utilized the reverse coding such that 1.00, which includes 10-13 correct answers, is considered good knowledge, 2.00, which includes 7-9 correct answers, is regarded as moderate knowledge, and 3.00, which includes six and below correct answers is considered poor knowledge. Thus, the lower the mean, the higher the knowledge. Therefore, if the mean difference between the two groups is negative, a positive attitude can be attributed to the group (I). Similarly, a negative attitude can be attributed to the group (I) if the mean difference is positive in value.

Table 9. *Level of Knowledge of the Respondents Based on Age*

	<i>df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	4	2.668	.034
Within Groups	195		
Total	199		

*Legend: *df* = degree of freedom; *F* = F-statistic; *Sig.* = significant difference

Table 9 presents the p-value between respondents' knowledge when grouped according to age. As can be seen, the p-value is less than 0.05, precisely p-value=0.034, which signifies a significant difference between the respondent's knowledge when grouped according to their age. The respondents' knowledge may be attributed to the quality of education received in different generations or the difference in curriculum learned in school. Moreover, various age-related factors, such as life experiences and societal influences, can also be influential. Given the different societal circumstances experienced by different generations, individuals who grew up in different eras may have distinct life experiences and be exposed to varying societal influences, which can shape their knowledge.

Additionally, societal changes or technological advancements could impact the knowledge acquired by the different age groups. This suggests that evolving external factors may influence knowledge attained within different age groups. Older individuals may likely rely on traditional sources of information. At the same time, younger generations are most likely to rely upon and benefit from the rapid technological changes, affecting the range and depth of their acquired knowledge. In a study conducted by Pogurshi et al. (2022), they also found that there is a significant difference in the knowledge of the respondents in terms of age. As a result, multiple comparison test was used to find which pairs have significant differences.

Table 10. *Result of the Multiple Comparison Test on the Level of Knowledge Based on Age*

<i>(I) Age</i>	<i>(J) Age</i>	<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
18-29	30-39	.35673*	.042
	40-49	.27778	.448
	50-59	.37778	.750
	60 and above	-.22222	.991
30-39	18-29	-.35673*	.042
	40-49	-.07895	.994
	50-59	.02105	1.000
	60 and above	-.57895	.776
40-49	18-29	-.27778	.448
	30-39	.07895	.994
	50-59	.10000	.998
	60 and above	-.50000	.865
50-59	18-29	-.37778	.750
	30-39	-.02105	1.000
	40-49	-.10000	.998
	60 and above	-.60000	.837
60 and above	18-29	.22222	.991
	30-39	.57895	.776

40-49	.50000	.865
50-59	.60000	.837

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

* Legend: Sig. = significant difference

Table 10 shows the significant difference in the level of knowledge of the respondents when grouped according to their age. As can be seen in the table, the age range that gained less than 0.05 is between 18-29 years old and 30-39 years old, in which they gained a p-value of 0.42. Moreover, based on their mean difference, the age bracket of 18-29 years old gained a positive mean, while the 30-39 years old had a negative mean. This implies that the older age group has better knowledge of antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance compared to the younger age group. It can be assumed that older individuals have had more exposure to various illnesses and treatments over their lifetime, which can contribute to a broader understanding of antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance. Likewise, the results of this study coincide with the study of Guo et al. (2021), who found that young adults (21-34 years old) have poor knowledge compared to older adults (above 50 years old).

Table 11. Knowledge of the Respondents Based on Educational Attainment

	df	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3	5.097	.002
Within Groups	196		
Total	199		

*Legend: df = degree of freedom; F = F-statistic; Sig. = significant difference

Table 11 shows the p-value between respondents' knowledge when grouped according to their educational attainment. As can be seen, the p-value is less than 0.05, precisely p-value= 0.034, which signifies a significant difference between the respondent's knowledge when grouped according to their educational attainment. Various factors related to the level and quality of education may influence the respondents' knowledge levels. One such factor could be the depth of knowledge acquired through different educational levels, where higher levels of education may indicate a better understanding of the subject matter. Furthermore, the availability of educational resources and the quality of educational institutions may differ across different levels of educational attainment, affecting the scope and accuracy of acquired knowledge. Moreover, practical experiences and the application of knowledge learned in specific educational settings may also contribute to differences in the respondents' overall knowledge levels. In the same study by Pogurshi et al. (2022), it was presented that there is a significant difference in the respondents' knowledge level about antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance according to the socio-economic income. As a result, multiple comparison tests were used to find which pairs have significant difference.

Table 12. Result of the Multiple Comparison Test on the Level of Knowledge Based on Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	(J) Educational Attainment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.
High school Undergraduate	High school Graduate	.23810	.854
	College Undergraduate	.39519	.446
	College Graduate	.71209*	.045
High school Graduate	High school Undergraduate	-.23810	.854
	College Undergraduate	.15710	.768
	College Graduate	.47399*	.031
College Undergraduate	High school Undergraduate	-.39519	.446
	High school Graduate	-.15710	.768
	College Graduate	.31689*	.018
College Graduate	High school Undergraduate	-.71209*	.045
	High school Graduate	-.47399*	.031
	College Undergraduate	-.31689*	.018

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

* Legend: Sig. = significant difference

Table 12 presents the significant difference in the level of knowledge of respondents when grouped according to their educational attainment. As can be seen in the table, the educational attainments that gained less than 0.05 are between high school undergraduate and college graduates, high school graduates and college graduates, and college undergraduate and college graduates. These gained 0.045, 0.31, and 0.18, respectively.

In addition, based on their mean difference, high school undergraduates, high school graduates, and college undergraduates gained a positive mean difference, which signifies that they have lower knowledge. Meanwhile, college graduates gained a negative mean difference, which signifies that they have better knowledge. It can be assumed that since college graduates have completed formal education, this provides them with a foundational understanding of healthcare practices. This education equips them with knowledge about antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance. However, it is crucial to note that having knowledge does not always translate into better attitudes and practices compared to the other levels of educational attainment.

The result of this study coincides with the study of Pogurshi et al. (2022), which showed that higher levels of education were significantly associated with a reduced likelihood of having inaccurate knowledge regarding antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance. People who had a postgraduate education were approximately ten times less likely to have inaccurate knowledge compared to people who only had a secondary education.

Table 13. *Knowledge of the Respondents Based on Socio-economic Status*

	<i>df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	6	1.840	.093
Within Groups	193		
Total	199		

*Legend: *df*= degree of freedom; *F*= F-statistic; *Sig.*= significant difference

Table 13 shows the p-value between respondents' knowledge when grouped according to their socio-economic status. As can be seen, the p-value is greater than 0.05, which signifies no significant difference between the respondent's knowledge when grouped according to their socio-economic status. It implies that regardless of the socio-economic status that a person belongs to, it is unlikely that those with higher status have better knowledge, and vice versa.

There are several reasons why there is not a significant difference in knowledge about antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance among people from different socio-economic backgrounds. First, information about these topics may be equally accessible to everyone, regardless of their economic status. This could be because healthcare facilities, educational programs, and media campaigns effectively disseminate information to the general public. Second, public health campaigns may have contributed to a more uniform level of knowledge across different socio-economic groups. Assuming that these campaigns are comprehensive and inclusive, they may have successfully reached and educated people from diverse backgrounds. Lastly, cultural factors could also contribute in the lack of socio-economic differences in knowledge. Some cultural norms may prioritize health education and awareness, leading to a more well-informed population across all socio-economic groups.

Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the respondents' knowledge of antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance when grouped according to socio-economic status is accepted. Likewise, this study coincides with the study of Yee Chow et al. (2021), where no significant difference in knowledge of antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance between participants of different socio-economic statuses was found. The result of Yee Chow was further supported by the research review of Al-Obaidi et al. (2021), which found a wide range of knowledge regarding antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance among participants, regardless of their socio-economic status. However, there was no clear evidence that participants with lower socio-economic status had less knowledge than those with higher socio-economic status.

Attitude of the Respondents Based on Demographic Profile

The analysis and interpretation of the difference in the respondents' attitudes when grouped according to their profile are based on the p-value of the ANOVA and the multiple comparison test. Furthermore, determining which group has the better attitude compared to another group is based on the mean differences. The verbal interpretation in the attitude section is categorized into four, where the lower mean signifies that the attitude leans toward the positive. In contrast, the higher the mean, the attitude leans toward the negative. Therefore, if the mean difference between the two groups is negative, a positive attitude can be attributed to the group (I). Similarly, a negative attitude can be attributed to the group (I) if the mean difference is positive in value.

Table 14. *Attitude of the Respondents Based on Age*

	<i>df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	4	10.372	.000
Within Groups	195		
Total	199		

*Legend: *df*= degree of freedom; *F*= F-statistic; *Sig.*= significant difference

Table 14 presents the p-value between the respondents' attitudes when grouped according to age. As can be seen, the p-value is less than 0.05, precisely p-value=0.000, which signifies a significant difference between the respondents' attitudes when grouped according to their age. Various factors, such as lived experiences and cultural narratives, can influence a person's attitude toward medication, particularly antibiotics. Different age groups have experienced varying levels of access to antibiotics. They may have witnessed the evolution of the antimicrobial resistance threat and the developed worldview toward the importance of the role of health professionals. Moreover, certain cultural beliefs may have different perspectives on illness and treatment, impacting their attitudes toward antibiotics. The study of Berdida et al. (2022) likewise explained that age, which was found to be significant, is one of the predictors of the respondents' attitudes regarding antibiotic use and resistance. The study found a "significant difference in participants' age in their attitudes in the acquisition, hygienic practices and role of health professionals in antibiotic resistance" (Berdida et al., 2022, p. 289). As a result, a multiple comparison test was performed to find which pairs have significant differences.

Table 15 reveals the result of the multiple comparison test that shows which pairs of variables have significant differences in

respondents' attitudes when grouped according to their age. As can be seen, the age range that gained less than 0.05 is between 18-29 years old and 30-39 years old with a p-value of 0.001, and between 18-29 years old and 40-49 years old with a p-value of 0.000. It signifies that respondents of these age groups differ in their attitudes toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance.

Based on their mean difference, the age bracket of 18-29 years old gained a negative mean value compared to the 30-39 years old and 40-49 years old who received a positive mean value. It implies that the younger age group has a more positive attitude toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance than the older age group. It can be assumed that since the younger age group was brought up in a more digital world where information can reach a vast population, they are more exposed to reliable information. Healthcare also became accessible during this generation, so the advice given by healthcare professionals is prevalent. These can be considered as contributing factors to the positive attitudes of the younger people compared to the older people.

Table 15. *Result of the Multiple Comparison Test on the Attitude Based on Age*

(I) Age	(J) Age	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.
18-29	30-39	-.31267*	.001
	40-49	-.54241*	.000
	50-59	-.21741	.796
	60 and above	-.65741	.198
30-39	18-29	.31267*	.001
	40-49	-.22974	.294
	50-59	.09526	.990
	60 and above	-.34474	.799
40-49	18-29	.54241*	.000
	30-39	.22974	.294
	50-59	.32500	.548
	60 and above	-.11500	.996
50-59	18-29	.21741	.796
	30-39	-.09526	.990
	40-49	-.32500	.548
	60 and above	-.44000	.732
60 and above	18-29	.65741	.198
	30-39	.34474	.799
	40-49	.11500	.996
	50-59	.44000	.732

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.
* Legend: Sig. = significant difference

Table 15 reveals the result of the multiple comparison test that shows which pairs of variables have significant differences in respondents' attitudes when grouped according to their age. As can be seen, the age range that gained less than 0.05 is between 18-29 years old and 30-39 years old with a p-value of 0.001, and between 18-29 years old and 40-49 years old with a p-value of 0.000. It signifies that respondents of these age groups differ in their attitudes toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance.

Based on their mean difference, the age bracket of 18-29 years old gained a negative mean value compared to the 30-39 years old and 40-49 years old who received a positive mean value. It implies that the younger age group has a more positive attitude toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance than the older age group. It can be assumed that since the younger age group was brought up in a more digital world where information can reach a vast population, they are more exposed to reliable information. Healthcare also became accessible during this generation, so the advice given by healthcare professionals is prevalent. These can be considered as contributing factors to the positive attitudes of the younger people compared to the older people.

The results of the study coincide with the findings of Effah et al. (2020), who found that younger respondents (18-34 years old) were more likely to have a positive attitude towards antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance than older respondents (50 years old and above).

Table 16. *Attitude of the Respondents Based on Educational Attainment*

	df	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3	10.149	.000
Within Groups	196		
Total	199		

*Legend: df= degree of freedom; F= F-statistic; Sig.= significant difference

Table 16 presents the p-value between the respondents' attitudes when grouped according to educational attainment. As can be seen, the p-value is less than 0.05, precisely p-value=0.000, which signifies a significant difference between the respondents' attitudes when grouped according to their educational attainment. This difference can be attributed to various factors, such as the individual's exposure to different knowledge and experiences and differences in the quality of education received. It is possible that those who have received a better quality of education may present a more positive attitude. Likewise, in the results of Nepal et al. (2019), it was presented that

there is a significant difference in the respondents' attitudes about antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance. As a result, a multiple comparison test was performed to find which pairs have significant differences.

Table 17 provides the result of the multiple comparison test that shows which variables have significant differences in respondents' attitudes when grouped according to their educational attainment. As can be seen, the educational attainments that gained less than 0.05 are between high school graduates and college graduates, with a p-value of 0.032, and college undergraduates and college graduates, with a p-value of 0.000. It signifies that the respondents who belong to these groups differ in their attitude toward the use of antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance.

Table 17. Result of the Multiple Comparison Test on the Attitude Based on Educational Attainment

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>(J) Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
High school Undergraduate	High school Graduate	-.00238	1.000
	College Undergraduate	.07069	.976
High school Graduate	College Graduate	-.30363	.300
	High school Undergraduate	.00238	1.000
College Undergraduate	College Undergraduate	.07308	.896
	College Graduate	-.30125*	.032
	High school Undergraduate	-.07069	.976
College Graduate	High school Graduate	-.07308	.896
	College Graduate	-.37432*	.000
	High school Undergraduate	.30363	.300
	High school Graduate	.30125*	.032
	College Undergraduate	.37432*	.000

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

* Legend: Sig. = significant difference

Based on their mean difference, the high school graduate and college undergraduate both gained a negative mean value compared to the college graduates who received a positive mean value. It signifies that those with lower educational backgrounds have a more positive attitude toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance than those with a higher educational background. However, it was observed that those belonging to the younger age group are currently students. Thus, these people have received a more timely and relevant education than those who graduated earlier.

Moreover, antibiotic resistance is a recently recognized concern that has been faced in the current state of society. It is more likely that these students are learning about this issue in school today compared to those who have finished college earlier. Hence, they are more familiar with and attentive regarding the proper consumption of antibiotics.

The result of this study is in contrast with most of the studies, which show the opposite trend. The result of Nepal et al. (2019) contradicts the result of the study by stating that people with higher levels of education are more likely to have better attitudes toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. They further supported that it may be caused by their likelihood of accessing information about these issues and understanding the importance of using antibiotics correctly.

Table 18. Attitude of the Respondents Based on Socio-economic Status

	<i>df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	3	10.149	.000
Within Groups	196		
Total	199		

*Legend: df= degree of freedom; F= F-statistic; Sig.= significant difference

Table 18 presents the p-value between the respondents' attitudes when grouped according to socio-economic status. As can be seen, the p-value is less than 0.05, precisely p-value=0.005, which signifies a significant difference between the respondents' attitudes when grouped according to their socio-economic status. Various factors related to the monthly income and the class to which a family belongs may influence the respondents' attitudes, such as the accessibility and affordability of antibiotics. It affects an individual's attitude in that easy access to and affordability of antibiotics may cause them to be more prone to taking antibiotics unnecessarily or vice versa. However, the result does not coincide with the study of Crucis et al. (2019), who reported that there is no significant relationship between the respondent's monthly income and their attitudes. As a result, a multiple comparison test was performed to find which pairs have significant differences.

Table 19 presents the result of the multiple comparison test that shows which pairs of variables have significant differences in the attitudes of respondents when grouped according to their socio-economic status. As can be seen, the socio-economic status that gained less than 0.05 is between the monthly income of less than Php 11 000 and Php 44 000-76, 999 with a p-value of 0.002. This implies that the attitude toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance of the respondents who belong to these groups differs.

Based on the mean difference, the monthly income of less than Php 11,000 is negative in value when compared to the monthly income of Php 44,000-76,999. This implies that those who have a monthly income of less than Php 11,000 are more likely to have a better attitude compared to those who have a monthly income of Php 44,000- 76 999. It can be assumed that those who have lower socio-economic status are likely to have access to support programs such as counseling from pharmacists and public health campaigns that promote awareness of antibiotics. Moreover, people with lower incomes have lower access to antibiotics and may not be able to afford them. It can result in them using traditional means of curing diseases, such as using herbal medicines and plants in the community. Thus, they are more likely not to be exposed to antibiotics compared to those who can afford them. On the other hand, individuals who have easy access and can afford antibiotics may be more likely to demand them from healthcare providers, even when they are not medically necessary.

Table 19. Result of the Multiple Comparison Test on the Attitude Based on Socio-economic Status

(I) Socio-economic Status	(J) Socio-economic Status	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.
<11 000	11, 000- 21, 999	-.11607	.900
	22, 000- 43, 999	-.22293	.083
	44, 000- 76, 999	-.39385*	.002
	77, 000- 131999	-.29107	.867
	132, 000- 219, 999	-.16607	.996
	220, 000	.01726	1.000
11, 000- 21, 999	<11 000	.11607	.900
	22, 000- 43, 999	-.10686	.951
	44, 000- 76, 999	-.27778	.255
	77, 000- 131999	-.17500	.991
	132, 000- 219, 999	-.05000	1.000
	220, 000	.13333	.999
22, 000- 43, 999	<11 000	.22293	.083
	11, 000- 21, 999	.10686	.951
	44, 000- 76, 999	-.17092	.685
	77, 000- 131999	-.06814	1.000
	132, 000- 219, 999	.05686	1.000
	220, 000	.24020	.972
44, 000- 76, 999	<11 000	.39385*	.002
	11, 000- 21, 999	.27778	.255
	22, 000- 43, 999	.17092	.685
	77, 000- 131999	.10278	1.000
	132, 000- 219, 999	.22778	.981
	220, 000	.41111	.744
77, 000- 131999	<11 000	.29107	.867
	11, 000- 21, 999	.17500	.991
	22, 000- 43, 999	.06814	1.000
	44, 000- 76, 999	-.10278	1.000
	132, 000- 219, 999	.12500	1.000
	220, 000	.30833	.973
132, 000- 219, 999	<11 000	.16607	.996
	11, 000- 21, 999	.05000	1.000
	22, 000- 43, 999	-.05686	1.000
	44, 000- 76, 999	-.22778	.981
	77, 000- 131999	-.12500	1.000
	220, 000	.18333	.999
220, 000	<11 000	-.01726	1.000
	11, 000- 21, 999	-.13333	.999
	22, 000- 43, 999	-.24020	.972
	44, 000- 76, 999	-.41111	.744
	77, 000- 131999	-.30833	.973
	132, 000- 219, 999	-.18333	.999

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.
 * Legend: Sig. = significant difference

The result of this study, however, did not correspond to the findings of Wattiheluw et al. (2020), which found that respondent’s attitudes toward the use of antibiotics had no relationship with household income, which means that the attitudes of the respondents do not differ when they are grouped according to income.

Overall, the researchers, therefore, reject the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the respondents’ attitudes on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance when grouped by age, educational attainment, and socioeconomic status.

Relationship Between Knowledge and Attitude to the Practice

The analysis and interpretation of the relationship between knowledge and practice together with attitude and practice was based on the rule of the Pearson Correlation, which states that if the p-value is less than 0.05, there is a significant difference between the variables. However, if it is greater than 0.05, there is no significant difference between the variables.

Table 20. *Correlation between Knowledge and Practice*

	<i>Pearson's r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>QD</i>
Practices ↔ Knowledge	0.088	0.217	Very Low Positive Correlation

Legend: *Pearson r*; Qualitative Description; +0.40 – +0.59; High Correlation; +0.80 – +0.99; Very High Correlation; +0.20 – +0.39; Moderately Low Correlation; +0.60 – +0.79; Moderately High Correlation; +0.01 – +0.19; Very Low Correlation; *Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Table 20 shows the relationship between the knowledge of the respondents and their practice toward the use of antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance. As can be seen, the p-value is equivalent to 0.217, which is higher than 0.05. Based on the analysis, at a 5% significance level, a very low positive correlation exists, but the relationship between the variables is not significant.

Therefore, the result implies that the knowledge and practices of the respondents do not influence nor relate to each other. It simply means that regardless of their level of knowledge, it does not relate to how they use antibiotics. Having no significant relationship suggests that the knowledge of the respondents, regardless of whether it is good, does not mean that the respondents will automatically perform good practice on the use of antibiotics. In the same way, the poor knowledge of the respondents does not necessarily mean that they will perform poor practices. This is evident in the results of the level of knowledge and practices of the respondents, wherein the majority of the population possesses good knowledge; however, they are performing poor practices. The results of the study are similar to the findings of Okedo-Alex et al. (2019), who state that there was a good level of knowledge about antibiotic use and resistance; however, practice levels were poor. The study concluded that medical schools should enrich existing courses and training about antibiotic use and give more emphasis on antimicrobial stewardship since their respondents were medical students.

Table 21. *Correlation between Attitude and Practice*

	<i>Pearson's r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>QD</i>
Practices ↔ Attitude	0.229*	0.001	Moderately Low Positive Correlation

Legend: *Pearson r*; Qualitative Description; +0.40 – +0.59; High Correlation; +0.80 – +0.99; Very High Correlation; +0.20 – +0.39; Moderately Low Correlation; +0.60 – +0.79; Moderately High Correlation; +0.01 – +0.19; Very Low Correlation; *Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Table 21 shows the relationship between the knowledge of the respondents and their practice toward the use of antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance. Based on the analysis, at a 5% significance level, there is a significant relationship between the attitude of the respondents and their practice toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. Based on the value of the Pearson Correlation, a moderately low positive correlation exists.

The result implies that if a respondent has a positive attitude toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance, the respondent will most likely have proper attitudes toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. Conversely, if a respondent has a negative attitude, then the respondent could perform improper practices toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. Given the result that the overall attitudes of the respondents were positive, there is a need for further improvement and supervision, so these positive attitudes can be retained and further developed. Through these, the population will be able to practice the proper utilization of antibiotics. The result of the study complies with the findings of Alnasser et al. (2021), which found that the highest correlation was found between the attitudes and practices of the respondents. Likewise, Dejene et al. (2022) reported a significant association between the respondents' attitudes and good practices regarding antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. It proposes that the attitudes of the respondents directly influence their practices.

Conclusions

Overall, the majority of the respondents have a good level of knowledge and a positive attitude toward antibiotic use and antimicrobial use. However, their practices were considered poor as they have shown inappropriate practices toward antibiotic use. Differences in the level of knowledge when grouped according to age and educational attainment were also found to be significant; however, no significant difference was shown in terms of socio-economic status. In terms of attitude, age, educational attainment, and socio-economic status were found to be influential as different categories from these groups possess varied attitudes. These results align with the report where knowledge does not have a significant relationship with the practices, indicating that having good knowledge does not mean a person performs good practices. Lastly, a moderately low positive correlation is significant between the attitudes and practices of the respondents, which implies that the more positive the attitude, the better their practices are and vice versa.

With the significant findings of the study, the researchers suggest the following recommendations:

The government, particularly the Local Government Units (LGUs) and health agencies of Bayombong, including the Department of Health (DOH), develop action plans and ordinances for the proper distribution of antibiotics among pharmacies to combat antimicrobial resistance.

The governing bodies can also conduct programs that will further educate the people, which can retain and improve their level of knowledge and attitude for the improvement of their practices on antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. Such programs can include seminars conducted in barangays, particularly far-flung areas, to disseminate information and educate community residents.

Medical practitioners should do their part by orienting patients properly, pharmacists should not disclose unprescribed antibiotics, and doctors should avoid medication errors.

Citizens of the province and the country should combat this global health issue through simple ways, such as disseminating information using various platforms, including campaigns. Other methods can be dissuading people to self-medicate and refrain from sharing antibiotics with others.

The citizens can likewise retain and improve their knowledge and attitude by becoming educated regarding the topic in order to improve their practices on antibiotic use. Such measures can include attending programs, consulting doctors, and listening and following the advice given by doctors and pharmacists.

For future researchers, it is recommended to have varied respondents for a more valid and equal distribution of the profiles of the respondents for more accurate and reliable results. The questionnaires should be equally distributed among various profiles, with equal distribution of the sample size, to ensure that the population being considered has equal representation.

Other variables, such as the influence of sex, culture, media, and community policies and regulations, can also be explored to further understand people's perceptions and practices toward antibiotic use.

The sample size should be increased, and it is recommended that future studies be conducted in places where the population is known to produce more accurate data to represent the population.

The questionnaire should be logically organized by arranging the questions and improving and modifying the translations to suit the chosen respondents.

The respondents should be adequately instructed and oriented regarding the contents of the questionnaire to avoid confusion and to ensure that all parts of the questionnaire are truthfully answered.

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